

DIGITAL ECONOMY AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES

Xasanova Aziza Kumushbek qizi

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Annotatsiya. Raqamli iqtisodiyotning hayotimizda tutayotgan o'ri, raqamlashtirilgan texnologiyalardan foydalanish, Al-Xorazmiy nomidagi universitetning raqamli iqtisodiyot sohasida tutgan o'ri, AKT ning yurtimizda rivojlanib borayotganligi.

Kalit so'zlar: kadrlar, innovatsiyalar, axborot, kommunikatsiyasi, texnologiyalar, strategiya, konsepsiya, infratuzilma.

Annotation. The role of digital economy in our lives, the use of digitized technologies, the role of Al-Khwarazmi University in the field of digital economy, the development of ICT in our country.

Keywords: personnel, Innovation, Information and communication, technology, strategy, concept, infrastructure.

Аннотация. Роль цифровой экономики в нашей жизни, использование цифровых технологий, роль университета Аль-Хорезми в области цифровой экономики, развитие ИКТ в нашей стране.

Ключевые слова: Кадры, инновации, информационные, коммуникации, технологии, стратегия, концепция, инфраструктура.

INTRODUCTION

In the current era of globalization, the demand for the digital economy is also increasing.

The digital economy and technology are rapidly expanding into all areas. Although it is still a new direction, it has completely covered the lifestyle of people. The growing popularity of the use of Information Communications is further developing the digital economy.

The term "digital economy" began to be used as early as 1995. It was first used by Nicolas Negroponte in his book "Being Digital"., A scientific work that proposed a convergence model based on three intersecting media networks (Media, (Media) Communications, and computers). As a result of such a merger, a new (digital) media was formed."

"The economy of a country without a digital economy has no future"
Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev

All over the world, digital technologies are rapidly entering the lives of all spheres and people. Countries that have entered this direction on time are developing, and those that have worked in an old way, on the contrary, are lagging behind in progress

2020 is declared the "year of development of Science, Education and digital economy" in our country, and a great deal of work has begun on this. In particular, on April 28, the decision of the head of our state "on measures for the widespread introduction of the digital economy and e-government" was adopted.

- Network and area leaders are obliged to understand that without digitization there will be no result, no development. Leaders at all levels should set this as a daily task for themselves and study the field of digitization in depth, starting with the alphabet, " Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted."

It can be seen that the digital economy serves as the foundation for the development of our state. For example, in the field of education, the head of the country also mentioned that several

reforms should be carried out. Notable examples include the construction of IT parks and the specialized school named after Al-Khwarazmi as well as the University.

Main part: Al Khwarazmi University was founded on the basis of the following goals and objectives. "Purpose:

Contribute to the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals in national, territorial and international communities by providing world demand level education, conducting modern research, cultivating creative talents and leaders, and integrating education and science with production.

Vision:

Future oriented education-creativity (Creativity)

Tashkent University of Information Technology named after Muhammad al-Khwarazmi is an educational institution that provides academic knowledge necessary for students to become highly qualified specialists and actively shapes the future of our country. The wide range of subjects offered by the university provides students with modern education and in turn represents the social and global functions of the University. Continuing education provides a foundation for lifelong learning as a component of university education. The concept of innovation is seen as an important foundation for the continuous improvement of the University. The university strives to ensure that the quality of education is at the level of World requirements by establishing a constant increase in the qualifications of teachers by supporting dialogues between professors and students.

Innovative infrastructure of science-capability (Ability)

The university is instrumental in forming a strategic alliance with companies, universities and non-university research institutes by supporting the exchange of knowledge and technology between science and production. The university supports innovation through spin-offs as well as the creation of companies.

Creation of spiritually mature talents-maturity (Maturity)

The university promotes being part of a regional and national network by conducting public discussions among student-youth and providing a place for creative, active and talented professionals in community life, as well as maintaining relationships with its alumni.

Digital University-Transparency (Transparency)

Providing modern and quality education will continue to contribute to achieving Sustainable Development Goals nationally and internationally by conducting scientific research to create new innovative developments."

Modern institute, University and schools can not be made ACT. Not only do they contribute significantly to the development of the economy, but they are based on world standards

Discussion: "Information and communication technologies in recent years

Quality associated with four cases in (ACT) development

shifts observed :

- digital technologies are constantly expanding their scope of application;
- * the costs of introducing and using the appropriate tools are constantly decreasing;
- the level of digitization of economic activity is constantly growing (including due to the influence of the first two factors);
- availability of digital devices (computers, phones, smart devices and devices connected to the Internet) and the distribution is constantly growing.

This set of cases is based on the development of digital ecosystems, supported by digital platforms, to the economic goal of new business models qualitatively new conditions for compliance led to formation .”

In the development of the digital economy, our state is implementing several measures, the economy on information and technological platforms is developing rapidly.

Conclusion: the development of the digital economy shows that our state is among the countries that are developing in the world.

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